

TWO MULTIPLE OF THE INTEGRAL APPLICATIONS .

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10570485>

ANNOTATION.

In the article economic processes image to do and of them other , economic indicators in the calculation use , income and cost concept and to them about integrals count studied. This , the economy analysis make , income and expenses manage for is used .

Key words: labor productivity of production, stock of products (goods), volume of product production, income function,

ANNOTATION.

In the article, the description of economic processes and their use in calculating other economic indicators, the concept of income and expenses and the calculation of their integrals are studied. This is used for the analysis of the economy, management of income and expenses.

Enter

Multiple integral, finance calculation in the field , for example , calculation perform and financial essence in the calculation done will be increased. Economic models and algorithms in making is used . Economical processes image to do and of them other , for example , economic indicators in the calculation used will be is used . This is the economy analysis make , income and expenses manage for applied. Investment activity and expenses , income , profit , loss , income increase and reduction , investment portfolio make up such as concepts in the calculation is used . Economical integral concepts in the field , costs and trade policy the problem analysis in doing is used . Trade policy and financial strategies in defining of the integral role important _

Coordinates according to two of the multiple integral mathematician structural is part of Mathematician in modeling a lot variable functions and of them user elements (eg for , surfaces , volumes) in integration is used .

1. $\iint_D f(x, y) dx dy$ in the integral $f(x, y) = 1$ if , $\iint_D dx dy$ integral D of the figure

face represents , that is

$$S = \iint_D dx dy$$

Example 1. $x = 4y - y^2$, $x + y = 6$ lines with limited of the field find the face

Solving . Given of lines intersection points we find

$x = 4y - y^2, x = 6 - y$ dan $4y - y^2 = 6 - y, y^2 - 5y + 6 = 0,$ intersection points will
 $y_1 = 2, y_2 = 3; x_1 = 4, x = 3; A(4;2)$ va $B(3;3)$

be So surface _ _

$$S = \iint_D dx dy = \int_2^3 dy \int_{6-y}^{4y-y^2} dx = \int_2^3 x \Big|_{6-y}^{4y-y^2} dy = \int_2^3 (4y - y^2 - 6 + y) dy = \int_2^3 (5y - y^2 - 6) dy =$$

$$= \left(\frac{5}{2} y^2 - \frac{y^3}{3} - 6y \right) \Big|_2^3 = \frac{1}{6} (\text{sq. unit})$$

2. From above $z = f(x, y)$ surface , from below $z = 0$ plane , from the side right cylindrical surface with and XOY in the plain D the field harvest who does cylindrical of the body size

$$V = \iint_D f(x, y) dx dy \text{ with the integral is counted .}$$

Example 2. $y = 1 + x^2, z = 3x, y = 5, z = 0$ surfaces with in the bounded I octant of the body size count _

Solving . Size be counted need the object is from above $z = 3x$ plane , from the side $y = 1 + x^2$ parabolic cylinder , $y = 5$ plain with limited . So as

$$V = \iint_D 3x dx dy = 3 \int_0^2 x dx \int_{1+x^2}^5 dy = 3 \int_0^2 x [5 - (1 + x^2)] dx = 3 \int_0^2 (4x - x^3) dx = 3 \left(4 \frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{x^4}{4} \right) \Big|_0^2 =$$

$$= 3 \left(2 \cdot 2^2 - \frac{2^4}{4} \right) = 24 - 12 = 12 \text{ куб.бop.}$$

3. Plate each _ at the point density function $\gamma(x, y)$ if , his mass

$$m = \iint_D \gamma(x, y) dx dy$$

with the integral is considered

Of the plate OX va OY to arrows relatively static moments.

$$M_x = \iint_D y \gamma(x, y) dx dy, M_y = \iint_D x \gamma(x, y) dx dy$$

formulas with is considered

Plate homogeneous , that is $\gamma = \text{const}$ when his weight of the center coordinates

$$\bar{x}_c = \frac{M_x}{S} = \frac{\iint_D x dx dy}{S} \quad \bar{y}_c = \frac{M_y}{S} = \frac{\iint_D y dx dy}{S}$$

formulas using is found on the ground S, D of the field face on the OX and OY axes of the plate relatively inertia moments

$$J_x = \iint_D y^2 \gamma(x, y) dx dy, \quad J_y = \iint_D x^2 \gamma(x, y) dx dy$$

formulas with γ , coordinates per head relatively inertia moment

$$J_0 = \iint_D (x^2 + y^2) \gamma(x, y) dx dy = J_x + J_y$$

with the formula is determined. Above in formulas $\gamma(x, y) = 1$ so flat of figures geometric inertia moments to find formulas we can

Example 3. $y^2 = 4x + 4$, $y^2 = -2x + 4$ lines with limited of the figure weight of the center find the coordinates.

Solving. Lines OY axis relatively symmetrical that it was for $\bar{y}_c = 0$ $\bar{x}_c$ the we find:

$$S = \iint_D dx dy = 2 \int_0^2 dy \int_{\frac{y^2-4}{4}}^{\frac{4-y^2}{4}} dx = 2 \int_0^2 \left(\frac{4-y^2}{4} - \frac{y^2-4}{4} \right) dy = 2 \int_0^2 \left(3 - \frac{3y^2}{4} \right) dy =$$

$$= 6 \left[y - \frac{y^3}{12} \right]_0^2 = 6 \left(2 - \frac{8}{12} \right) = 8$$

$$\bar{x}_c = \frac{1}{S} \iint_D x dx dy = \frac{1}{8} 2 \int_0^2 dy \int_{\frac{y^2-4}{4}}^{\frac{4-y^2}{4}} x dx dy = \frac{1}{8} \int_0^2 \left[\frac{4-y^2}{4} - \frac{(y^2-4)}{16} \right] dy = \frac{1}{8} \int_0^2 \left(3 - \frac{3}{2} y^2 + \frac{3}{16} y^4 \right) dy =$$

$$= \frac{1}{8} \left(3y - \frac{y^3}{2} + \frac{3y^5}{80} \right)_0^2 = \frac{2}{5}. \text{ So } C\left(\frac{2}{5}; 0\right).$$

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